

THE EROSION OF SMALL STATES – BETWEEN FOREIGN POLICY OPPORTUNISM AND INTERNAL OBSTACLES: CASE STUDY – WESTERN BALKANS

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Abstract

The main purpose of this paper is to put an emphasis on the internal institutional challenges, risks and threats on the path of creating sustainability at different levels. Thus, authors have decided to create a comparative analysis between internal, mostly institutional challenges, risks and threats, from one side, and foreign policy goals from the other side. Mentioned analysis would be, on the empirical example of Western Balkans, basis for proving the thesis that small states with limited political, economic, security and resource capacities should ensure their effective foreign policy positioning, thus ensuring sustainability, through strong, strategically directed and tactically adaptable institutional framework. In that context, the research question of the study would be: Does the weak institutional framework of small and microstates with limited capacities and resources constitute the main determinant of their stability and sustainability? The study will use internal challenges, risks, and threats as a variable in the process of concretizing and proving the promoted thesis.

Key words: small states, weak institutions, foreign policy, internal challenges, risks and threats, Western Balkans

1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of sustainability and sustainable development the institutional framework is positioned also as one of the goals of the whole process from the global perspective. But, the main issue of the discussion in this paper is the realization of the sustainable development agenda, thus reaching the declared goals, from the institutional perspective of small states. Precisely, how much small states in the group of weak ones, with a weak, unstable and unpredictable institutional system, could contribute to the mentioned agenda, thus securing sustainability as well for itself, and could play effective role on micro (national) level, if those group of countries produces internal (domestic and authentic) challenges, risks and threats with contrary consequences to the SDGs agenda? The authors leading question would be: on which grounds small and weak states could establish the sustainable development strategy framework if there is a lack of efficient institutional mechanism for the management and realization process? And it is closely connected to the declared foreign policy goals of small and weak states because their

foreign policy goals are defined on the national interests preservation basis. Analysed from that perspective, preservation of national interests is the basis for sustainability, which leads us to the finding that realization of foreign policy goals is in cause-and-effect relationship with national sustainable development. Namely, a weak domestic institutional framework is not able to perform strategically based and tactically focused diplomatic actions for the realization of foreign policy goals. Diplomatic failure on the side of foreign policy goals is questioning the national capabilities for the preservation of national interests. Without mechanism for preservation the long-term defined national interests, sustainable development of such groups of states is, by logical reasoning, unreachable. In fact, there is the essential importance of the paper, respectively, the explanation about the link between weak institutional framework and foreign policy failures which consequences are directly related to sustainability, including the development. From such perspective, on the concrete example of the Western Balkans states and political entities, authors will justify their thesis about the essential importance of internal institutional system and its effectiveness, as a precondition in the process of sustainable development, especially in the case of small states with limited economic, political, natural and military resources. From a theoretical perspective, authors will use the explanation of the representatives of neoclassical realism who are using the personal dimension of authorities/political and institutional representatives. Precisely on the case study of the Western Balkans, and through the mentioned theoretical dimension, the authors will explain how political and institutional authorities in the context of weak institutional framework are misusing their official capacities, working de facto against the foreign policy agenda and preservation of national/state interests, thus questioning the sustainability of the state they represent. The empirical example of foreign policy failure in the case study region, based on personal, instead of institutional decisions and guidelines, will serve as a pragmatic explanation of the authors' thesis, as well as empirical verifiable evidence about the importance of institutional system in the general context of sustainable development, as well as in the micro context of small states. This study also lead us to the wider discussion about the institutional efficiency and effectiveness, positioned as one of the sustainable development goals. Namely, the question that arises is whether the professional, predictable and stable institutional framework should still be set as one of the goals or they should be repositioned as one of the preconditions on the SDGs agenda?

2. METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

The research will be methodologically framed in qualitative methods, which refer to qualitative data analysis in order to determine behavioural patterns (Arežina, 2023:209) of the case study political entities in the context of foreign policy positioning. In fact, authors through the foreign policy activism are identifying the research problem which in this case is the issue of sustainability of small and weak states. Further, through the analysis of data (European Commission Annual Reports) they are establishing the description of the main phenomenon related to national/domestic institutional weakness as a dependent variable in the whole process of reaching strategic foreign policy goals, thus achieving effective foreign policy positioning which as a result means preservation of national/state interests and finally, securing sustainability. The research question (Creswell, 2012 :60) is structured so that the authors could be able to concretize the global sustainability phenomenon on a specific problem, respectively, to reach a specification of the problem of sustainable development from the perspective of small and at the same time weak states.

From a scientific perspective, the aim of this paper is to provide a scientific explanation (Arežina, 2021 :278) of the consequences that political decision-makers create in their personal and extra-institutional foreign policy activism in contemporary international relations, thus deepening the debate on the role of leaders in creating foreign policy from the perspective of neoclassical realists. On the other hand, in the context of societal goals, i.e. the applicability of this research (Arežina, 2021 :278), the authors provide a forecast based on existing tendencies derived from the annual reports of the European Commission, which further strengthens the value of the analysis itself, making it useful in identifying internal/domestic challenges, risks and threats and its implication to foreign policy positioning and sustainability as a de facto linked processes from the perspective of relationship between foreign policy goals and national/state interests. In the context of concretization and raising the question why the authors have decided to use European Commission Annual Reports as a sufficient data analysis basis, the explanation lies in the declarative foreign policy strategic goal of empirical example entities which is EU membership. From the perspective of the EU membership, as a goal which, in the context of case study entities, should contribute to further stability and development, authors have made quite a reasonable decision to use mentioned data of the reports as a qualitative explanation basis for dependent variable found in the institutional system and political framework. Methodologically, the paper is focused to internal dependent variables, isolating them on the case study of foreign policy decision-making process from the neoclassical realism theoretical approach, thus providing explanation about the sustainability of small and weak states.

3. POLITICAL POPULISM AND THE CAPTURE OF INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK

In order to be clear during the process of analysing so-called small states, first we should clarify the difference between two subgroups of small states: small states with efficient and effective institutional framework and small states with captured institutional framework which, in practice, make those political entities weak and vulnerable. The goal of this paper is to analyse the process of so-called erosion of small and weak states from the institutional perspective, bearing in mind the limited capacities of resources that generally small states have. In fact, authors are focused to explain, on the Western Balkans case study, that lack of political, diplomatic, economic, natural and military resources could be on a certain way substituted with the strong, efficient, effective, resistant and reliable internal institutional framework, as a kind of an unlimited resource which could play a role of "fuel" in reaching defined foreign policy goals, thus securing sustainability of national interests, including the sustainability of the state.

The Western Balkans region has been chosen because there are states and political entities with enormous internal and regional issues, disputes and obstacles which, on a long-term basis, have negative effects not only in the process of creation sustainability, but in the rounding off statehood process. Empirical example serves twofold: to represent the characteristics of small and weak states, from one side; from the other side, to explain the role of institutional framework in the process of realization foreign policy goals and, consequently, securing sustainability.

As data for proving the thesis, the authors will use the European Commission Annual Reports for each of the so-called Western Balkans Six. The decision for analysis mentioned reports has twofold justification: first, those are annual documents which are strictly and precisely in different areas following the internal processes of Western Balkans

Six; second, EU membership represents a key, as well as strategic foreign policy goal of each of the Western Balkans Six, so there is logic connection between internal challenges, risks and threats, from one side, and foreign policy goals, from the other side.

Belgrade (Serbia 2024 Report, 2024)	
Internal challenges, risks and threats	
Political	political polarisation, existence of a list of “morally and politically unwelcome foreigners”, widespread pressure on public sector employees, EU integration process centralised and politically driven, political influence on the media
Economic	economic uncertainty, state-owned enterprises have a significant presence in the economy, economic influence on the media, private sector is hampered by weaknesses in the rule of law, in particular in tackling corruption and judicial inefficiency, the link between the strategic priorities and budget programmes is insufficient, and ad hoc priorities frequently crowd out resource allocation
Institutional	Serbia should address weaknesses in the investigation and prosecution of high-level corruption cases, the risk of corruption remains high for cases of exemptions from the Law on public procurement that are not in line with the EU acquis, Serbia ranked 104th out of 180 countries in the 2023 corruption perception index compiled by Transparency International, thus continuing the negative trend since 2018

Skopje (North Macedonia 2024 Report, 2024)	
Internal challenges, risks and threats	
Political	political polarisation in Parliament persisted, the situation was polarised during the period preceding the elections of April and May 2024, political support, leadership, supervision, and management of public administration reforms across the government remained insufficient, politicisation of the public service has continuously undermined the consistent application of provisions on merit-based and transparent processes and has further decreased trust in the administration and its work
Economic	post-pandemic economic recovery remained weak, economy remains vulnerable to a potential renewed surge in energy prices, given its high energy-intensity and still large reliance on imported energy, challenges posed by the large informal economy have not been addressed decisively, despite the urgent need to modernise the

	economy's infrastructure, investment in this area is low
Institutional	Health is one of the biggest national budget users, and the inspection services are vulnerable to corruption, corruption remains prevalent in many areas and is an issue of serious concern, track record in the fight against corruption has worsened, there are still concerning patterns regarding an increasing number of delays in court proceedings and an increase in reversals of court rulings on corruption and organised crime

Sarajevo (Bosnia and Herzegovina 2024 Report, 2024)	
Internal challenges, risks and threats	
Political	The reform dynamic stalled between April and October 2024, among political controversies and the political campaign for the October local election, political parties should respect the independence of the Central Election Commission, the conduct of the elections is negatively affected by the discriminatory elements of the constitutional system and by the lack of integrity of the electoral process, parliamentary oversight over the executives remains weak
Economic	Financial investigations and asset seizures and confiscations remain insufficient, Bosnia and Herzegovina is at an early stage of preparation and has made limited progress in establishing a functioning market economy, countrywide harmonisation remains insufficient, hindering progress towards a single economic space, the business environment continues to suffer from a weak rule of law, political uncertainty and the country's economic and institutional fragmentation
Institutional	Bosnia and Herzegovina needs to bring its constitutional framework in line with European standards and ensure the functionality of its institutions to be able to take on EU obligations, Bosnia and Herzegovina will need to reform its institutions to be able to effectively participate in EU decision-making and to fully implement and enforce the acquis, Bosnia and Herzegovina lacks strategic documents as it still needs to adopt a new justice sector reform strategy and related action plan

Tirana (Albania 2024 Report, 2024)	
Internal challenges, risks and threats	
Political	The functioning of democratic institutions is partially

	satisfactory, stemming mainly from the deeply polarised political situation, unaddressed shortcomings in the electoral process, limited effective parliamentary oversight over the executive and the lack of meaningful public consultations. Political scene continued to be marked by high political polarisation against the background of persistent divisions within the largest opposition party. This has further weakened the effectiveness, transparency and objectivity of parliamentary work
Economic	The business environment is hampered by a large informal economy. Informal economy remains widespread, impacting fair competition among businesses, inefficiencies in public administration, an excessive regulatory framework and corruption pose further challenges to the business environment
Institutional	Concerns remain about attempted interference and pressure on the judicial system from public officials and politicians, despite strong legal safeguards, merit-based appointments and career development are weakened in practice

Podgorica (Montenegro 2024 Report, 2024)	
Internal challenges, risks and threats	
Political	Persisting fragmentation of the parliamentary landscape, political instability, Montenegro should further strive to align its electoral processes to highest democratic standards
Economic	The dynamic development of local and foreign companies is hindered by the informal economy, inefficiencies and delays in dealings with the administration, excessive complexity of the legal framework and the administrative burden related to parafiscal charges as well as insufficient quality of e-services. Further obstacles are related to insufficient transparency in decision-making, arbitrary law interpretation and enforcement by public authorities and access to finance for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)
Institutional	Institutions are fragile and vulnerable to political crisis and potential institutional blockages, political instability as a main reason for the lack of public administration reform, selection processes for managerial positions are subject to political influence, the judiciary and the prosecution remain perceived as vulnerable to political interference

Priština (Kosovo* 2024 Report, 2024)	
Internal challenges, risks and threats	
Political	Domestic politics hampered the implementation of EU agenda, lack of demonstration of political commitment by aligning its legislation with the EU acquis, politicization of humanitarian issues, lack of political will, the functioning of democratic institutions is affected by some challenges, such as lack of cooperation on the line majority-opposition, boycott, issue of centralization of executive decision-making
Economic	Vulnerable to political influence and financial pressure, tax base continues to be weakened by numerous tax exemptions, preferential tax rates and special regimes, while public spending is burdened by category-based specific transfers, leaving little space for means-tested benefits and employment policies, lacks an independent monetary policy and does not have standard monetary policy tools at its disposal
Institutional	From the rule of law perspective, government officials tend to criticise decisions in individual cases or even target specific judges or prosecutors, which is of concern, The quality of justice remains insufficient, precisely, the quality of indictments and judgments in criminal law remains insufficient, the prosecution service to handle cases in a timely manner remains limited, particularly in high-level corruption cases

Referring to the findings of European Commission Annual Reports for each of the Western Balkans Six represent a sufficient twofold methodological approach: first, to explain the internal context between political populism and real flows; second, to create stable basis for connections between internal institutional flows and foreign policy opportunism. But the second variable will be explained in the next chapter.

When it comes to the findings of European Commission Annual Reports and internal populist discourse, it is quite a clear that there are substantive disagreements. While, on internal level, political representatives are promoting their political programmes for continuation of the development and sustainability, from the other side, based on the reports which are strictly connected to the strategic foreign policy goal of each of the six entities, there are data which show contrary flows.

- ***In the context of democratisation***, EU reports have confirmed the thesis about the lack of political will for realistic strengthening of democratic capacities while, at the same time, leading domestic and political representatives are placing themselves as generators of democratic and open societies

- ***In the context of rule of law and fight against corruption***, EU reports are confirming the thesis about the lack of efficient political and institutional mechanisms for dealing and resolving mentioned internal risks while, at the same time, leading domestic

and political representatives are de facto encouraging the wide spreading of the phenomena of corruption, thus marginalizing the rule of law standards.

- *In the context of market economy*, EU reports are confirming the thesis about the inefficient market economy while, at the same time, leading domestic and political representatives are, through legislative and political tools, contributing to the creation of a kind a politically-based economy which could not be interpreted as a planned economy, inherent to socialist or communist systems, but beneficial to the politically favourable groups and interests.

In fact, Western Balkans Six are facing structural internal (domestic) challenges, risks and threats, politically projected and institutionally applicable which are influencing to enhancing the process of complete internal inefficiency, which leads to unpredictability to whole process of sustainability, thus negatively contributing to the internal erosion. Within such scenario composed of public discourse based on the political populism, capture of institutional framework within the political interests and the lack of social and political awareness about the referred negative political, economic and institutional trends lead case study entities to the general twofold erosion: internal, by producing domestic challenges, risks and threats from institutional to social framework and vice-versa and foreign, lack of efficient political tools and institutional mechanisms for foreign policy positioning based on the foreign policy goals and defined national (state) interests. Data analysis based on the European Commission Annual Reports has shown concrete example about the dependence of foreign policy positioning to the internal (domestic) functionality. In the case study political subjects foreign policy positioning is absolutely released of their own material possibilities and resources and structurally based to the qualitative conditions framed in the domestic institutional system based on the political, economic and social frames. Such a context leads the authors to the conclusion that foreign policy opportunism is not a consequence of international developments, in this case within the European Union framework, but rather a “hostage” of domestic challenges, risks, and threats that generate structural contradictions within the political framework. While this framework formally insists on defined foreign policy goals, it simultaneously fails to contribute to domestic institutional functionality, which functions as a dependent variable in achieving the desired foreign policy positioning.

4. FOREIGN POLICY FAILURES FROM REGIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL PERSPECTIVE

This chapter serves to create a connection between the foreign policy goals of the political entities in the Western Balkans region and the institutional (domestic) challenges, risks and threats from the perspective of erosion of the state. Namely, each of Western Balkans Six declared the EU membership as a key and strategic foreign policy goal. In the case of Belgrade, the European integration and membership in the European Union are placed as a goals even above the foreign policy goals, stating that the both processes are "the national interest and strategic commitment of the Republic of Serbia, while the values of the European Union are precisely the values that the Republic of Serbia supports and wishes to further foster" (Republika Srbija, Ministarstvo spoljnih poslova, Politički odnosi Srbije i EU, 2025). In fact, Arnaudov explains, "Western Balkans exists as a political entity in which it is precisely European integration that determines such an whole, outside the real geographical framework on the ground" (Arnaudov, 2023 :124). But, the available data witness that the European integration and the EU membership are, in practice, just a

declarative or official goal of each of Western Balkans Six. Such thesis is empirically explained in the previous chapter where we have made short review of the political, economic and social flows within of each of the Western Balkans entities. Each of Western Balkans Six is facing intensive internal issues, risks and challenges, overspread in political, economic and institutional infrastructures, thus contributing to the national or precisely systematic inability to deal, manage and lead the foreign policy process in the context of European integration and EU membership.

Recalling the well-known Copenhagen criteria, each of Western Balkans Six has not established internal institutional infrastructure, thus political and economic grounds which will sustainably secure “stability of institutions guaranteeing democracy, the rule of law, human rights and respect for and protection of minorities, a functioning market economy and the ability to cope with competitive pressure and market forces within the EU, the ability to take on the obligations of membership, including the capacity to effectively implement the rules, standards and policies that make up the body of EU law (the ‘acquis’), and adherence to the aims of political, economic and monetary union” (EUR-Lex/Accession criteria (Copenhagen criteria):¹⁹⁹³).

On the contrary, there is a lack of an establishing framework for reaching the elementary criteria of European integration process and EU membership, although on the formal, official and legislative level there are visible results. But, the lack of consistency between legislative and implementation flows is the major obstacle. Political and institutional representatives in practice do not express realistic political will for the EU membership and integration process, thus questioning the so-called leading foreign policy goal. Consequently such scenario leads Western Balkans Six to the stage of unpredictability for two reasons: at internal (domestic) level, institutional, political and economic framework are instrumentalized in practice by political representatives, thus losing their main role and task to serve to the nation and the state; at international level, even in the current geostrategic momentum, Western Balkans Six are losing international and European support in the context of integration process because could not be positioned as reliable partners due their internal challenges, risks and threats, while, from the other side, all six entities are not making contribution to achieving defined criteria, thus not convincing the EU member states about their realistic dedication to integration process and membership.

Additional negative value in the whole process are current regional flows. Namely open issues and disputes since the civil wars from nineties and politization of the mentioned period, instrumentalization of bilateral issues in the European integration processes, continuation of the cross-border negative political rhetoric which raises animosities and reinforces the ground of distrust on a regional basis, including the lack of realistic understanding and political will about the Belgrade-Priština dialogue represent also important barriers to the foreign policy positioning of the Western Balkans Six entities, especially in the process of reaching key and strategic foreign policy goal of EU membership. The internal flows stated in this way remind us of the title of this paper, namely that it is about foreign policy opportunism, given that nothing substantial and concrete is being done in the process of achieving foreign policy goals, but rather that the actors in the politically defined region of the Western Balkans are preoccupied with internal and regional, primarily politically determined, trends and discourses that contribute to the destruction of the internal institutional infrastructure through its political instrumentalization, while at the same time distancing political entities from achieving foreign policy goals, and making them unsustainable if we strictly adhere to the theoretical

premise that achieving foreign policy goals serves the preservation and sustainability of national interests.

5. NEO-CLASSICAL REALISM AS AN APPROACH

Neoclassical realists argue that relative material power establishes the basic parameters of a country's foreign policy. They note, in Thucydides' formula, that "the strong do what they can and the weak suffer what they must" (Strassler, 1996 :5.89 op.cit. u: Rose, 1998 :146). Yet they point out that there is no immediate or perfect transmission belt linking material capabilities to foreign policy behaviour. Foreign policy choices are made by actual political leaders and elites, and so it is their perceptions of relative power that matter, not simply relative quantities of physical resources or forces in being. This means that over the short to medium term countries' foreign policies may not necessarily track objective material power trends closely or continuously (Rose, 1998 :147). Concretely, neoclassical realists believe, understanding the links between power and policy requires close examination of the contexts within which foreign policies are formulated and implemented (Steinmo et al., 1992 :11 op.cit. u: Rose, 1998 :147). The most common approach has been to assume that foreign policy has its sources in domestic politics (Rose, 1998 :148). It is the crucial theoretical approach, as a basis for making linkage between the functionality of domestic institutional framework and foreign policy positioning. Concretely, from the perspective of empirical examples in the second chapter of the paper, neoclassical realists are providing explanation about the cause-effect relationship between internal (domestic) challenges, risks and threats, from one side, and the process of achieving declared foreign policy goals – EU integration and membership. According to these stands, sustainability, as an issue closely dependent of foreign policy positioning, also is mostly determined by political decisions, respectively the behaviour of political and institutional representatives. Such thesis opens new debates for understanding the global phenomena of sustainability, thus placing the dependent variable of political decision-making process in the whole context of progressive sustainability. Unlike classical realists, who analyse foreign policy positioning exclusively from the perspective of the relationships between subjects in the international system (Rose, 1998 :146), neoclassical realists offer a more comprehensive understanding that significantly contributes, among other things, to the understanding of the foreign policy positioning of small and weak states. In this research by proving the linkage between domestic flows and foreign-policy positioning, at the same time released of the material variables, authors have opened a frame for new and qualitative discussion about the ongoing and future prospects of sustainability, thus sustainable development, basing the whole process on institutionality and political behaviour. Empirical paper is based to the so-called *Innenpolitik* theories which argue that internal factors such as political and economic ideology, national character, partisan politics, or socioeconomic structure determine how countries behave toward the world beyond their borders (Rose, 1998 :148). There are many variants of the *Innenpolitik* approach, each favouring a different specific domestic independent variable, but they all share a common assumption – that foreign policy is best understood at the product of country's internal dynamics (Rose, 1998 :148).

The author's assumption is that such theories are primarily applicable in the current chapter of international relations with the focus of small and microstates. Thus, making a clear twofold difference between material and qualitative variables in the foreign policy activism and positioning, while, from the other side, understanding about the small and microstates with strong institutional and personal (labour market) capacities and that one

positioned as a weak state. The first difference is classical one, from the perspective of classical realists, states with political power and military and economic strength could lead effective foreign policy activism, while, at the same time, there is a lack, from classical realists' perspective, understanding for qualitative variables, as those are personal (labour market) capacities, institutional strength and expertise based foreign policy strategies and tactics. From the small and microstates position, the difference between sustainable and weak states lies exclusively in the qualitative variables, respectively characteristics taking into account authors' assumption that small and microstates generally are facing limited resources and capacities, but still they have unlimited capacities and resources in the context of institutions functionality and personal solutions.

6. CLOSING REMARKS

Using the case study of the European integration process of Western Balkans Six, as well as the EU membership positioned as a key and strategic foreign policy goals of each of the Western Balkans political entities, paper' authors has significantly contributed to the understanding about the internal and substantial variables in the process of foreign policy positioning on the examples of small states. Authors have decided to use empirical example of small and weak states in order to create clearer picture about the domestic institutional factor, as a resource, in the process of foreign policy activism, thus reaching foreign policy goals as a mechanism for securing national/state interests. At the same time, on the side of sustainability, using the logic that defined foreign policy goals are serving as an instrument for preservation of national/state interests, authors have explained that without effective foreign policy positioning, thus losing the opportunities for reaching foreign policy goals, the national/state interests are directly endangered. By endangering the national/state interests, sustainability of the subject of the international system is as well questioned. Back to the title of the research, erosion of small states is directly dependent by internal institutional obstacles and the lack of synchronization between domestic political management and foreign policy approach. In fact, this is a characteristic of small but, first of all, weak states. Without domestic and foreign policy synchronization, followed by abusing foreign policy goals and national/state interests on daily political basis, instrumentalization of national institutional infrastructure for political, interest and personal needs, the foreign policy success would be missed, while, at the same time the erosion of the state infrastructure will be empowered due to the lack of mechanisms for preservation the national/state/social interests. Referring to the positions of neoclassical realists, small states cannot create effective and efficient strategic and tactic plans for their own foreign policy activism based exclusively on the international politics flows, behaviour of regional and big powers, current relations of regional and big powers, if they lack to include, as a variables, domestic institutional, political and social flows, including potential challenges, risks and threats. In fact, domestic functionality of small states is a key mechanism for their foreign policy visibility. Although those type of states are faced with a permanent lack of material resources, in the context of foreign policy positioning, as well as in the context of sustainable development, their domestic institutional reliability and political behaviour, including personal behaviour of political and state representatives, could play significant, even a crucial role in the process of reaching defined foreign policy goals, as a precondition for preserving national/state interests, thus securing sustainability.

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